

MEDICAL SCIENCES

ERRORS IN THE DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF CHRONIC RECURRENT APHTHOUS STOMATITIS IN CHILDREN

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Abstract

Ambiguity of views on the etiology and pathogenesis of chronic recurrent aphthous stomatitis leads to frequent diagnostic errors and, as a result, to incorrectly prescribed treatment. At the present stage, there are a large number of drugs and methods for treating chronic recurrent aphthous stomatitis in children, but a complete algorithm for complex therapy has not been developed. There are no methods of maintenance therapy, which remains an urgent task in pediatric dentistry and requires further research.

Keywords: children, chronic recurrent aphthous stomatitis, diagnostics, treatment.

Introduction. Chronic recurrent aphthous stomatitis (CRAS) is one of the common diseases of the mucous membranes of the oral cavity in children. At the same time, there is still no consensus on the etiology of this pathology [1, 2]. In the world literature, many reports are devoted to the etiological role of the microflora of the oral cavity and digestive tract in the development of this disease. Some the authors established the dependence of the occurrence diseases from vitamin balance, constitutional predisposition [3, 6]. Together with the clinical and experimental data indicate that recurrent aphthae oral cavity occur against the background of dysfunction and pathology of the digestive tract, immune system and other concomitant diseases [4,5]. One of the most popular theories development of CRAS in children is sensitization body in response to some stimulus allergen, i.e. allergic nature of the disease. Thus, the achievements of recent years point to the fact that CRAS does not occur as a purely local disease of the oral mucosa, but is a manifestation of the general pathology of the child's body [6].

Ambiguous views regarding etiology and pathogenesis of chronic recurrent aphthous stomatitis leads to frequent diagnostic errors [7, 8] and, consequently, to the absence of a stable therapeutic effect. Diagnosis of CRAS in children, given the multifactorial nature of this mucosal pathology membranes of the oral cavity, is quite complex process. It provides for the evaluation of anamnestic, clinical and laboratory data, as well as differential diagnosis with aphthous lesions of the oral mucosa of another etiology. Data on the frequency and nature of diagnostic errors, as well as analysis of the results treatments for chronic relapsing aphthous stomatitis in childhood is insufficiently covered in the literature.

The purpose of this study: to study errors in the diagnosis and treatment of CRAS and the causes, causing these errors.

Materials and methods. 84 medical histories of children with chronic relapsing aphthous stomatitis who sought help from the Department of Pediatric Dentistry of the Bukovyna State Medical University and are under dispensary registration at the Children's Dental

Polyclinic in Chernivtsi were analyzed. Distribution of children by age: from 3 up to 7 years - 69, from 7 to 14-16; by gender: girls - 48, boys – 36. call, as well as evaluated the results and methods of treatment.

Results of research and discussion. The analysis carried out showed that the catheter diagnosis with a diagnosis made in the clinic coincided only in 56% of cases. In 32% of cases, there was a discrepancy, and in 12% of cases, patients came without a diagnosis. essential diagnostic the mistake is to use practical doctors in 78% of cases for chronic recurrent aphthous stomatitis term "allergic stomatitis", which is absent in the generally accepted classification of allergic diseases of the oral mucosa.

Another diagnostic mistake is to underestimate the importance of the full collection anamnesis of the disease and life of the child, which suggests the allergic nature of the disease, narrow the range of search for causal significant allergens, assess the somatic status of the child. Analysis of children's case histories showed that only 15 (17.4%) have information about aggravated allergic history in the form of indications of allergic reactions in parents child or recurrence of aft. And this, in its turn, leads to an underestimation of the overall state child and his constitution, and because of this, no adjustment in the general therapy of the disease.

An equally important error at the stage of diagnosis is the absence in almost 100% of cases of consultations with related specialists - pediatricians, gastroenterologists, hematologists, allergists, and others, as well as the absence of results of additional research methods. Lack of understanding by physicians of the importance of identifying and treating comorbidities by appropriate specialists in of this contingent of patients leads to an aggravation of the course of the disease, as evidenced by a high percentage (76%) of relapses.

Attention is drawn to insufficient use (94%) or incorrect interpretation (72%) of modern diagnostic methods (immunological, allergological, scatological, etc.), which is absolutely unacceptable for chronic recurrent aphthous stomatitis [4, c. 55-60]. In our opinion, the insufficient knowledge of practicing doctors of

the clinical manifestations of chronic recurrent aphthous stomatitis in children also leads to diagnostic errors.

Thus, the causes of diagnostic errors can be multifactorial, conditionally into two groups.

Non-medical:

- low culture of the population;
- untimely visit to the dentist;
- socio-economic conditions.

Medical:

- incomplete collection of anamnesis;
- underestimation of the general condition and his child constitutions;
- lack of complete knowledge about the nature of diseases;
- incorrect morphological interpretation of the diagnosis;
- insufficient use or incorrect interpretation of the results of modern methods diagnostics (immunological, allergological, cytological, etc.)

The above reasons, and often their combination, lead to errors in the diagnosis, therefore, to inadequate treatment and unstable therapeutic effect of chronic recurrent aphthous stomatitis, recurrence of the disease.

However, since traditionally the classical idea of the leading role in the pathogenesis of chronic recurrent aphthous stomatitis of food allergens, quite often the basis of CRAS therapy in children is the unreasonable prescription of a hypoallergenic diet. She provides for exclusion from the diet during several weeks of obligate allergens, and this, most often, red vegetables and fruits, potatoes, Dairy products are the main sources of vitamins and microelements. The error is that the appointment of such a hypoallergenic diet leads to insufficient intake of vitamins in the child's body, and, therefore, further exacerbates indicators of general and local immunity in the direction of their decrease. Such therapy can be justified only in case of confirmation of antigenic properties of food components immunological methods and obtaining stable therapeutic the effect of the treatment: reducing the duration of treatment, lengthening the period of remission, reducing the number of relapses of the disease, which is rarely achieved with traditional treatment. Analysis case histories of children showed that such conventional CRAS therapy without laboratory data carried out in 94%.

Errors and practical miscalculations of practitioners in the local treatment of CRAS in children:

- emphasis in the vast majority of cases (82%) is done only on symptomatic treatment;
- selection of an inadequate scope of interventions: 3-4 unidirectional drugs for local treatment, in particular, anti-inflammatory, for example 2% solution of copper sulfate, givalex, chlorophyllipt, etc.;
- unreasonable refusal of anesthesia when treatment of elements of rashes on the oral mucosa (74%);
- rough processing of the oral mucosa without taking into account age-related structural features mucosa leads to spreading and deepening elements of damage and, thereby, to the deterioration the general condition of the child and an increase in the duration of treatment.

Errors in general treatment include the following:

- complete absence of general treatment in 68% of cases;
- antihistamines are prescribed in 56% of cases first generation drugs (suprastin, tavegil, etc., which have many side effects, and in in other cases, antihistamines are not prescribed at all;
- there is no adjustment of treatment in accordance with the somatic status of the child;
- very rarely (13%) funds are assigned, normalizing the local and general immune response.

Thus, the lack of a unified view of the etiology and pathogenesis of chronic recurrent aphthous stomatitis in children leads to diagnostic errors, leading, in turn, to aggravate the general condition of the child associated with the lack of a therapeutic effect.

Conclusions. The frequency of medical errors in the diagnosis and treatment of CRAS in children is associated with the lack of unity of approaches to the etiology and pathogenesis of this diseases. For this reason, in our opinion, must be provided in the protocols for the provision dental care standard including in addition to immunomodulators, modern means, reducing the level of sensitization, etiotropic therapy after identifying the source of allergization.

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